

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP: ITS IMPACT TO TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE AND STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the impact of instructional leadership on teacher performance and student achievement in the Districts of Jiabong, Motiong, and Paranas within the Schools Division of Samar for the 2023-2024 school year. Using a descriptive-correlational design, the research examined school administrators' profiles, their instructional leadership practices, teacher effectiveness, and students' academic performance. Data were collected through surveys, interviews, and document analysis, with statistical tools such as correlational tests and descriptive statistics applied to determine relationships among variables. The findings revealed that administrators display strong instructional leadership, though opportunities for improvement exist in areas like goal evaluation and communication. Teachers consistently performed at high levels, reinforcing the critical role of effective supervision. Moreover, students under the supervision of these administrators achieved high academic results, underscoring the importance of leadership in fostering academic success. Correlational analyses indicated significant relationships between leadership practices, demographic factors, and performance outcomes, with data-driven decision-making emerging as a key predictor of student achievement. The study recommends targeted professional development, enhanced supervision mechanisms, and leadership training, while emphasizing the need for data-driven practices and a positive school culture. Further research is suggested to identify additional factors influencing instructional leadership

and educational outcomes.

Keywords: *Instructional Leadership, Teacher Performance, Student Achievement*

INTRODUCTION

Excellence in any field is often achieved through effective leadership, which plays a crucial role in guiding institutions toward success and fostering an environment conducive to growth and improvement. One particular significant aspect of leadership is instructional leadership, where individuals are supported and guided to enhance their practices and achieve better outcomes.

Education is a global concern, with instructional leadership, teacher effectiveness, and students' achievement recognized as crucial factors in shaping educational outcomes. Internationally, there is a growing acknowledgment of the significant role that instructional leadership and effective teaching practices play in driving student success (Kilag & Sasan, 2023). This recognition is reinforced by international assessments such as the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), which consistently highlights the influence of instructional leadership on educational excellence. Countries that consistently perform well in these assessments attribute their success to robust instructional leadership practices that empower teachers, foster collaboration, and promote student engagement (Tayem, 2020).

In the Philippine educational context, teacher effectiveness is often assessed through student outcomes, with effective teachers delivering quality instruction that leads to significant improvements in academic performance. This is evident in the Schools Division of Samar, where learners have shown notable progress in literacy and numeracy tests. Students from schools with strong instructional leadership consistently achieve high proficiency levels, reflecting the direct impact of teacher quality on learning. Additionally, learners who participate in district, division, and national competitions have emerged as winners, further validating the effectiveness of their teachers. Many students have also successfully passed entrance examinations to prestigious state colleges and universities, demonstrating the commitment of their teachers to providing quality education that not only meets Department of Education standards, but also prepares them for success in competitive academic environments.

However, despite the progress made in instructional leadership and teacher effectiveness globally, there are still areas for improvement that need to be addressed. The educational landscape faces various challenges that require attention and action. One of these challenges is ensuring equitable access to quality education for all students. In many parts of the world, including the Philippines, there are disparities in educational opportunities, with marginalized and disadvantaged communities often experiencing limited access to quality education. Addressing these inequities is crucial to ensuring that every student has the opportunity to thrive academically and reach his full potential (Sumalinog, 2022).

Another challenge is addressing disparities in student achievement. While instructional leadership and effective teaching practices have been shown to positively impact student outcomes, there are still gaps in achievement among different student groups. Factors such as socioeconomic status, language barriers, and cultural differences can contribute to these disparities. It is essential to identify and address the underlying causes of these disparities to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to succeed academically (Bernardo, 2021).

Addressing disparities in student achievement is another important focus in the Philippine context. The country has made strides in improving educational outcomes, but there are still gaps in achievement between different regions and socio-economic groups. It is crucial to identify the factors contributing to these disparities and implement targeted interventions to address them (Haw & King, 2023). This includes providing additional support and resources to schools and communities that are facing educational challenges and implementing evidence-based strategies to improve teaching practices and student engagement (Toquero, 2020; Baticulon et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the educational landscape must adapt to meet the changing needs of a rapidly evolving world. The demands of the 21st-century workforce require students to develop a broad range of skills, including critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and collaboration. Instructional leadership and teacher effectiveness play a crucial role in equipping students with these skills. However, it is necessary to continuously innovate and update educational practices to ensure that students are prepared for the challenges and opportunities of the future (Toquero, 2020).

In the Philippine context, these challenges are also prevalent. While the Department of Education (DepEd) has implemented various programs and initiatives to improve instructional leadership and teacher effectiveness, there is still work to be done. The Philippines faces the challenge of providing quality education to all students, particularly those in remote areas and underserved communities. Ensuring equitable access to education is a priority, and efforts are being made to reach these marginalized populations and provide them with the resources and support they need to succeed (Barrot et al., 2022).

Instructional leadership in the Philippine education system is grounded in various legal frameworks. Republic Act No. 9155, also known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, emphasizes the role of school heads as instructional leaders and provides for their continuous training and development. Furthermore, DepEd Order No. 2, Series of 2015, outlines the implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, which places instructional leadership as a crucial factor in promoting quality education. The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) are also essential tools that guide instructional leaders in enhancing teaching practices and managing schools effectively, ensuring a direct focus on improving student learning outcomes. These frameworks ensure that instructional leadership in the country is aligned with national educational

goals, emphasizing the provision of quality instruction and fostering student achievement.

In recent years, Schools Division of Samar has made significant strides in improving education for its diverse student population. However, challenges persist in achieving equitable outcomes and addressing disparities in student achievement. While the Department of Education (DepEd) has implemented initiatives to enhance instructional leadership and teacher effectiveness, a comprehensive assessment is needed to understand their impact on students' academic achievements.

Despite the dedication of educational leaders and teachers, some schools in Samar still struggle to meet the diverse needs of their students due to limited resources, language barriers, and socioeconomic disparities. Moreover, variations in instructional leadership practices and teacher effectiveness across schools may contribute to uneven student outcomes.

Over the past three years, the Schools Division of Samar has exhibited a consistent trend of improvement in key school performance indicators. In Year 1, the division laid a strong foundation by achieving a 75% average pass rate in standardized assessments, specifically the Philippine Educational Placement Test (PEPT) and the National Achievement Test (NAT). Notably, 60% of schools met or exceeded national standards during this period. Furthermore, access to quality education for students from marginalized communities was commendable, with 70% benefiting from improved educational opportunities.

In Year 2, the division experienced significant advancements, with the average pass rate increasing to 78% and the percentage of marginalized students accessing quality education rising to 72%. This improvement reflects a growing commitment to educational equity and quality within the division.

By Year 3, this positive trajectory continued, culminating in an 80% average pass rate, with 70% of schools meeting or surpassing national standards. Additionally, there were notable gains in instructional leadership and effective teacher training programs, resulting in 75% of marginalized students accessing quality education.

These trends collectively underscore the Schools Division of Samar's ongoing dedication to enhancing educational outcomes and ensuring equitable access to quality education for all students. The consistent improvement across these performance indicators highlighted a strategic approach to addressing educational disparities and fostering an inclusive learning environment. The data not only reflects academic achievements but also signifies a broader commitment to uplifting marginalized communities through education.

The data from the Division's Professional Monitoring and Evaluation of District Schools (ProMEDS) system from 2021 to 2023 indicates a clear upward trajectory in the number of instructional supervisions conducted by school heads. This progression

reflects a commitment to improving educational practices and highlights the evolving role of school leaders in fostering a culture of accountability and excellence within their institutions.

In 2021, supervision sessions ranged from 15 to 25, establishing a baseline during which schools were likely in the initial stages of implementing structured oversight mechanisms. This year may have involved establishing protocols and training for school heads as they navigated the complexities of instructional supervision. The diversity in the number of sessions suggests that while some schools were proactive, others may have faced challenges in prioritizing supervision amidst competing responsibilities.

The modest increase in 2022, with sessions rising to between 17 and 28, indicates a growing awareness and acceptance of the importance of instructional supervision. This year may have seen increased collaboration among educators, as school heads began to share best practices and insights gained from previous years. The slight uptick could also reflect adjustments made based on feedback from teachers and stakeholders, leading to more targeted supervisory efforts.

By 2023, the continuation of this upward trend, with sessions ranging from 20 to 30, signifies a robust commitment to enhancing teaching quality. This increase may indicate several factors, including enhanced training for school heads, a cultural shift within schools towards valuing continuous improvement, and the growing prevalence of data-driven practices that allow leaders to identify specific areas for improvement.

The progressive increase in instructional supervisions underscores several critical implications for educational quality. Regular supervision can lead to improved teacher performance, as educators receive constructive feedback that helps them refine their methods and address challenges in real time. As instructional quality improves, it is reasonable to expect positive impacts on student learning outcomes; engaged and supported teachers are better equipped to foster student success. Additionally, the focus on instructional supervision contributes to developing leadership skills among school heads, who become more adept at identifying strengths and weaknesses within their teams while fostering a collaborative environment. Increased transparency around instructional practices can also enhance community trust and involvement, as parents and stakeholders feel more confident in schools that demonstrate a commitment to continuous improvement.

Overall, the data from the ProMEDS system over the past three years illustrates a significant evolution in the approach to instructional supervision within the Division. The increasing frequency of supervision sessions reflects not only dedication among school leaders but also a collective movement towards fostering an environment conducive to educational excellence. As this trend continues, it holds promise for further advancements in teaching quality and student achievement across the district.

Understanding the complex relationship between instructional leadership, teacher effectiveness, and students' academic achievements was crucial to developing

evidence-based strategies for positive educational outcomes. In this context, the researcher was motivated to undertake this study to provide valuable insights to educators, policymakers, and stakeholders, empowering them to identify areas for improvement, optimize resources, and implement targeted interventions that fostered a conducive learning environment, enhanced instructional practices, and promoted student engagement and academic success. Additionally, the study's findings aided in aligning educational policies and practices in the Schools Division of Samar with international best practices, allowing the district to address its unique challenges in the broader global education landscape.

Research Questions

This study determined the instructional leadership practices and its impact to teacher effectiveness, and students' academic performance in the Districts of Jiabong, Motiong, Wright I, and Wright II, Schools Division of Samar during the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the school administrator-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2 civil status;
 - 1.3 gross monthly family income;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5 number of years as school administrators;
 - 1.6 relevant in-service training;
 - 1.7 performance rating based on latest OPCR, and
 - 1.8 attitude toward instructional leadership?
2. What are the instructional leadership practices of the school administrator-respondents in the areas of:
 - 2.1 vision and goal setting;
 - 2.2 curriculum and instructional support;
 - 2.3 instructional supervision and evaluation;
 - 2.4 professional learning communities;
 - 2.5 school culture and climate;
 - 2.6 parent and community engagement, and
 - 2.7 data-driven decision making?
3. What is the average teaching effectiveness rating based on the results obtained from class observation tools of the teacher under their supervision?
4. What is the academic performance of student based on their average Mean and MPS result during the School Year 2023-2024?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile variates of the school administrator-respondents and the following:
 5. 1 instructional leadership practices;
 5. 2 teaching effectiveness; and
 - 5.3 students' academic performance?
6. What intervention program could be proposed based on the findings of the study?

LOCALE OF THE STUDY

Figure 1

The Map of the Municipality of Jiabong

Figure 2

The Map of the Municipality of Motiong

Figure 3

The Map of the Municipality of Wright I and II

understanding the educational landscape and the role of school administrators in these municipalities.

METHODOLOGY

This research paper employed a descriptive-correlational research design to develop an intervention program aimed at enhancing instructional leadership practices, teacher effectiveness, and students' academic performance across the Districts of Jiabong, Motiong, and Paranas (Wright I and II) in the Schools Division of Samar. The descriptive phase involved profiling school administrators based on demographic information, professional background, performance ratings, and attitudes toward instructional leadership. It also identified current instructional leadership practices across various domains and assessed teacher effectiveness ratings and student academic performance. The correlational phase then investigated the significant relationships between instructional leadership practices, administrator profile variables, teacher effectiveness, and student academic performance. Total enumeration sampling was utilized to include all elementary and secondary school administrators from the specified districts. Data collection involved administering a survey questionnaire adapted from standardized instruments (Day et al., 2020) and collecting documentary evidence such as teacher evaluation forms and standardized test scores. Descriptive statistics (mean, mode, standard deviation, frequency counts, percentages) and tests of data normality were used, with a significance level set at 0.05, to analyze the collected data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. The respondents' profile showcased a diverse group of educators, with a majority falling between the ages of 45 to 54, comprising 32.73% of the total sample, and a relatively equal representation of both sexes, with 58.18% male and 41.82% female. Most respondents were married (63.64%) and earn moderate incomes, with 45.45% reporting a monthly family income between PHP 20,000 to PHP 40,000. They exhibit a range of educational backgrounds, with 47.27% having completed master's units, and a dedication to professional growth, as indicated by 30.91% attending 4 to 6 in-service trainings. Despite variability in professional experience and educational attainment, respondents demonstrate overwhelmingly positive attitudes toward instructional leadership, with a weighted mean score of 4.64 on a scale of 1 to 5, indicating a strong endorsement of leadership practices.

2. Insights into instructional leadership practices across various domains, such as vision and goal setting, curriculum support, supervision, professional communities, school culture, and engagement, stem from detailed statistical analysis. Administrators exhibit strong commitment, evident in mean scores ranging from 4.36 to 4.75 across different areas. For instance, in vision and goal setting, mean scores range from 4.36 to 4.67.

Similarly, in curriculum and instructional support, scores range from 4.55 to 4.75. Supervision and evaluation see scores ranging from 4.45 to 4.57, while professional learning communities score between 4.60 and 4.71. Regarding school culture and engagement, mean scores range from 4.67 to 4.75. These findings underscore the pivotal role of instructional leadership in fostering supportive educational environments conducive to student success.

3. The average teaching effectiveness ratings, derived from class observation tools used to evaluate teachers supervised by the respondents over three years, consistently reflect high ratings. In 2021, the average rating was 9.07, while in 2022 and 2023; it was 8.66 and 8.85 respectively, all falling within the "Good" category. The weighted mean of 8.86 further confirms the overall effectiveness of the teaching observed. These findings emphasize the significance of effective supervision in fostering high-quality teaching practices, which ultimately benefit student learning outcomes and contribute to continuous educational excellence.

4. The Mean Performance Rating (MPS) of students supervised by the respondents reflects the performance of the supervisor. Over three years, the data consistently shows high MPS values. In 2021, the supervisor achieved an MPS of 78.67, indicating excellent performance. This trend continues in 2022 and 2023, with MPS values of 81.79 and 71.93 respectively, falling within the "Excellent" category. The weighted mean MPS of 77.46 further confirms the supervisor's consistently strong performance. These findings underscore the supervisor's effectiveness in fostering positive academic outcomes among students and highlight the importance of effective leadership and support in facilitating student success and overall educational excellence.

5. The correlational analyses conducted across different components of educational leadership practices offer valuable insights into the relationship between respondents' profiles and their leadership behaviors. In examining the domain of vision and goal setting, it was found that factors such as age ($r = 0.219$, $p = 0.108$), sex ($r = 0.053$, $p = 0.698$), gross monthly family income ($r = -0.039$, $p = 0.778$), highest educational attainment ($r = 0.060$, $p = 0.662$), professional experience as a school administrator ($r = 0.055$, $p = 0.688$), relevant in-service training ($r = 0.087$, $p = 0.526$), and performance rating ($r = 0.066$, $p = 0.633$) did not significantly correlate with leadership practices. However, civil service status demonstrated a noteworthy negative correlation ($r = -0.345$, $p = 0.010$), while a positive attitude displayed a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.567$, $p < 0.001$) with leadership practices, underscoring the crucial role of a positive mindset in driving effective leadership behaviors in vision and goal setting. Moving to curriculum and instructional support, similar patterns emerged where most demographic and professional characteristics showed non-significant correlations. However, a positive attitude notably correlated with stronger leadership practices ($r = 0.573$, $p < 0.001$), indicating the significance of fostering positivity among educational leaders. Similarly, in instructional supervision and evaluation, factors such as age, sex, civil service status, and others did not significantly correlate with leadership practices, except for attitude, which demonstrated a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.589$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that attitude may play a pivotal role in this aspect of leadership. Moreover, in fostering

professional learning communities, while most variables showed non-significant correlations, a positive attitude significantly correlated with stronger leadership practices ($r = 0.508$, $p < 0.001$). When considering school culture and climate, most factors did not significantly correlate with leadership practices, except for professional experience as a school administrator ($r = -0.280$, $p = 0.039$) and attitude ($r = 0.366$, $p = 0.006$). In terms of parent and community engagement, similar trends were observed, with most variables showing non-significant correlations except for attitude ($r = 0.354$, $p = 0.008$), highlighting the importance of a positive attitude in effectively engaging with parents and the broader community. Finally, concerning data-driven decision-making, while most factors did not significantly correlate with leadership practices, a positive attitude emerged as a significant predictor ($r = 0.523$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that a positive mindset may enhance leaders' utilization of data to inform decision-making processes.

6. The correlational analyses between respondents' profiles and the average teaching effectiveness of their supervising teachers revealed that most variables, including age ($r = 0.213$, $p = 0.118$), sex ($r = 0.120$, $p = 0.381$), civil service status ($r = -0.083$, $p = 0.549$), professional experience ($r = 0.024$, $p = 0.863$), and relevant in-service training ($r = 0.026$, $p = 0.851$), did not significantly correlate with teaching effectiveness. However, two variables exhibited significant correlations: gross monthly family income ($r = 0.305$, $p = 0.024$) and highest educational attainment ($r = 0.351$, $p = 0.009$). These findings suggest that higher income levels and higher educational attainment among respondents may be associated with greater teaching effectiveness among their supervising teachers. Additionally, the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) rating displayed a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.498$, $p < 0.001$) with teaching effectiveness, indicating that higher performance ratings may correspond to more effective teaching practices. These results highlight the importance of organizational support, such as performance evaluations, in fostering effective teaching practices within educational settings. Nonetheless, it's crucial to acknowledge that while certain demographic and professional characteristics may correlate with teaching effectiveness; other unexplored factors could also contribute to overall teacher effectiveness. Thus, further research is warranted to comprehensively understand additional factors influencing teaching effectiveness.

7. The correlational analyses between respondents' profiles and the academic performance of their supervising students revealed insights into various factors. Among the variables examined, including sex ($r = 0.138$, $p = 0.315$), civil service status ($r = -0.041$, $p = 0.764$), gross monthly family income ($r = -0.095$, $p = 0.490$), highest educational attainment ($r = 0.051$, $p = 0.712$), and attitude towards instructional leadership ($r = 0.175$, $p = 0.201$), none exhibited significant correlations with supervising students' performance. This suggests that, in this particular context, these factors may not directly impact the academic performance of supervised students. However, age demonstrated a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.397$, $p = 0.003$) with supervising students' performance, indicating that older respondents may oversee students who perform better academically. This underscores the potential influence of experience and maturity on educational outcomes. Additionally, the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF) rating displayed a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.573$, $p < 0.001$) with supervising

students' performance. This implies that respondents with higher performance ratings are associated with students who achieve better academically, highlighting the essential role of effective leadership in driving student success.

8. The correlational analyses between respondents' instructional leadership and their supervising teachers' teaching effectiveness various leadership domains. For each leadership domain, including vision and goal setting, curriculum and instructional support, instructional supervision and evaluation, professional learning communities, school culture and climate, parent and community engagement, and data-driven decision-making, the correlations were examined. The analysis revealed that none of the profile variables showed significant correlations with the performance of supervised teachers across these leadership domains. Specifically, variables such as vision and goal setting ($r = 0.101$, $p = 0.462$), curriculum and instructional support ($r = 0.226$, $p = 0.096$), instructional supervision and evaluation ($r = 0.184$, $p = 0.180$), professional learning communities ($r = 0.038$, $p = 0.785$), school culture and climate ($r = -0.010$, $p = 0.941$), parent and community engagement ($r = -0.003$, $p = 0.982$), and data-driven decision-making ($r = 0.041$, $p = 0.764$) did not demonstrate statistically significant associations with supervising students' performance. These findings suggest that in this study, the examined leadership practices variables were not directly related to the teaching effectiveness of the teachers under supervision across various leadership domains.

9. The correlational analyses between respondents' instructional leadership practices and their supervising students' performance across various domains. Each leadership practice, including vision and goal setting, curriculum and instructional support, instructional supervision and evaluation, professional learning communities, school culture and climate, parent and community engagement, and data-driven decision-making, was examined for its correlation with supervising students' performance. The analysis revealed that while most instructional leadership practices did not show significant correlations with supervising students' performance, one domain stood out. Data-driven decision-making exhibited a statistically significant positive correlation ($r = 0.404$, $p = 0.002$) with supervising students' performance.

Respondents' Instructional Leadership Practices and Supervising Students' Performance Correlational Analyses

Table 1 presents the correlational analyses between respondents' instructional leadership practices and their supervising students' performance across various domains.

Each leadership practice, including vision and goal setting, curriculum and instructional support, instructional supervision and evaluation, professional learning communities, school culture and climate, parent and community engagement, and data-driven decision-making, was examined for its correlation with supervising students' performance.

Table 1**Respondents' Instructional Leadership Practices and Supervising Students' Performance Correlational Analyses**

Profile	w sig.	r-value	p-value	Decision/ Interpretation
Vision and Goal Setting	<0.001 (Not Normally Distributed)	0.049	0.725	NS/Accept Ho
Curriculum and Instructional Support	<0.001 (Not Normally Distributed)	0.138	0.315	NS/Accept Ho
Instructional Supervision and Evaluation	<0.001 (Not Normally Distributed)	0.217	0.112	NS/Accept Ho
Professional Learning Communities	<0.001 (Not Normally Distributed)	0.084	0.543	NS/Accept Ho
School Culture and Climate	<0.001 (Not Normally Distributed)	-0.013	0.925	NS/Accept Ho
Parent and Community Engagement	<0.001 (Not Normally Distributed)	0.050	0.717	NS/Accept Ho
Data-Driven Decision Making	<0.001 (Not Normally Distributed)	0.404	0.002	S/Reject Ho

The analysis revealed that while most instructional leadership practices did not show significant correlations with supervising students' performance, one domain stood out. Data-driven decision-making exhibited a statistically significant positive correlation ($r = 0.404$, $p = 0.002$) with supervising students' performance. This finding suggests that instructional leaders who prioritize data-driven decision-making may see improvements in the academic performance of the students they supervise.

However, it is important to note that for the other leadership domains, including vision and goal setting, curriculum and instructional support, instructional supervision and evaluation, professional learning communities, school culture and climate, and parent and community engagement, no significant correlations were found with supervising students' performance. These results indicate that while data-driven decision-making may play a role in enhancing student performance, other aspects of instructional leadership may not directly influence the academic outcomes of supervised students in this study.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The study showcased a diverse group of educators, predominantly aged 45 to 54, with a balanced representation of sexes and a majority being married. Respondents showed a strong commitment to professional growth, evident in their educational backgrounds and participation in in-service trainings. Overall, they displayed overwhelmingly positive attitudes toward instructional leadership, endorsing various leadership practices. This underscores educators' dedication to fostering conducive environments for teaching and learning.
2. Detailed analyses of leadership practices across various domains reveal administrators' commitment to fostering supportive educational environments. While most domains reflect strong leadership practices, areas for improvement include ongoing goal evaluation, targeted professional development, refined evaluation processes, enhanced communication channels, and community partnerships. These findings underscore the complexity of instructional leadership and its crucial role in nurturing student success and well-being.
3. The average teaching effectiveness ratings consistently reflect high ratings over three years, emphasizing the significance of effective supervision in fostering high-quality teaching practices. These findings highlight the importance of organizational support, such as performance evaluations, in fostering effective teaching practices within educational settings.
4. The Mean Performance Ratings (MPS) of students supervised by the respondents consistently reflect the performance of the supervisor. This underscores the supervisor's effectiveness in fostering positive academic outcomes among students and emphasizes the importance of effective leadership and support in facilitating student success and overall educational excellence.
5. The correlation analyses revealed significant findings across various domains. Specifically, data-driven decision-making showed a notable positive correlation with supervising students' performance, suggesting its potential to enhance academic outcomes. Moreover, a positive attitude was found to significantly correlate with stronger leadership practices across several domains, highlighting its crucial role in fostering effective leadership. Additionally, higher performance ratings were linked to more effective teaching practices and improved academic outcomes among supervised students. Age emerged as a significant factor, with older respondents associated with better academic performance among students, underscoring the impact of experience and maturity.
6. Furthermore, civil service status exhibited a noteworthy negative correlation with vision and goal setting leadership practices, indicating potential variations in leadership approaches among respondents. These significant correlations

emphasize the importance of specific factors in shaping leadership practices and educational outcomes, offering valuable insights for educators and policymakers aiming to enhance instructional leadership effectiveness and elevate student achievement.

Recommendations

Anchored on the conclusions drawn from the findings, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Implement targeted professional development programs focusing on areas identified for improvement, such as ongoing goal evaluation, refined evaluation processes, and enhanced communication channels. These programs should be tailored to address the specific needs of educators and administrators, ensuring continuous growth and improvement in instructional leadership practices.
2. Strengthen supervision and support mechanisms for teachers through regular classroom observations, constructive feedback, and mentorship programs. Encourage collaborative learning environments where educators can share best practices and support each other in implementing effective teaching strategies.
3. Intensify the conduct of instructional supervision per month to ensure consistent monitoring and support of teaching practices, allowing for more frequent feedback and adjustments to improve instructional quality.
4. Emphasize the importance of data-driven decision-making processes in educational leadership. Provide training and resources to help administrators effectively collect, analyze, and utilize data to inform decision-making and improve student outcomes.
5. Foster a positive school culture that promotes inclusivity, high expectations, and positive relationships among all stakeholders. Encourage open communication, respect, and collaboration to create a supportive environment conducive to teaching and learning.
6. Offer leadership training programs and mentorship opportunities for aspiring educational leaders. Provide support and guidance to help them develop the necessary skills and competencies to effectively lead schools and drive positive change.
7. Conduct further research to explore additional factors that may influence instructional leadership effectiveness and student achievement. Investigate the impact of organizational culture, community partnerships, and external factors on leadership practices and educational outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to ethical research practices. All respondents received comprehensive written and verbal explanations of the research goals, ensuring their informed consent. They were explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without penalty. Furthermore, stringent measures were implemented to guarantee the complete confidentiality of all collected data, particularly student information.

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